

COMMUNICATIVE FEATURES OF SOCIAL DEIXIS IN ENGLISH WORK OF
ART (LEGEND OF THE SWORD .2017.MOVIE).

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Annotation: *This article discusses about communicative features of social deixis and some examples found in King Arthur: Legend of the Sword (2017) Movie . Also, it identifies some examples of types of deixes : relational deixes and absolute deixis, social relationships between speaker and hearers based on social factors in Legend of the Sword.*

Keywords: *Social deixis, social factors, relational deixis, absolute deixis*

Abstract: *This article deals with the importance of communicative features of social deixis in English work of ,as well as types of social deixis.*

Keywords: *social deixes, social factors, relational deixes, absolute deixes*

In recent years, literature is crucial to broaden our horizon and to know the past. We face up with some terms during reading works of art. Social deixis is one of such terms. First of all, I am going to give some information what social deixes itself. Social deixes marks “social connections in phonetic expressions with reference to the social status or part of members within the discourse event” . A few etymology in this manner see social deixis as a portion of individual deixis. The way we organize our expressions is impacted by our and our addressee’s social rank and our relationship to the other members of the discourse occasion. In numerous dialects this fact is reflected within the pronominal framework which distinguishes between a formal and an casual address within the moment individual pronoun. Such a separation is called T/V qualification motivated by the French shapes tu et vous . As is for the most part known the modern English does not take after such a refinement in spite of the fact that the Early Advanced English did. When individuals communicating, we utilize a customized dialect to which we are communicating, since the utilize of the dialect here may show grants, and social status. In communication, we moreover utilize a moniker that shows nature, regard and social status.

For the example of communication can be described as below:

Mr Tono : **Andi**, why did you come late?

Andi : I'm sorry **sir**. I passed the bus.

Mr. Tono : I will let **you** sit down if you answer my question. Who is the third president of Indonesia?

Andi : I do not know **sir**.

Mr. Tono : I will punish **you**. **You** must stand up in front of class for 10 minutes.

Andi : OK **sir**.

The conversation above can be seen in the view of the oral and written text.

In conversation, usually to get information of the listener, the speaker asks the listeners. For example the conversation above is uttered by Mr. Tono as teacher and asks to Andi as students. When Mr. Tono calls "**Andi**" and Andi replied "**Sir**", it is viewed Mr.Tono as someone who is older and respected.

Then, it is also viewed relation between Mr.Tono and Andi as teacher and student. Meanwhile, Andi, Sir and you are studied in Pragmatics, especially Deixis. According to Leech, "pragmatics is the study of the how utterances have meanings in situations".

The study of pragmatics embraces presupposition, implicature, entailment, speech

act, and deixis. So, it demonstrates that the deixis is an element of pragmatic study.

Deixis also is used refer to speaker, who or what that mean in speech, although when time in speech, it is happen. It is called sentence context, so deixis also laced the context. Deixis is element of pragmatics study.

Now we discuss types of Social deixis in examples in Legend of the Sword.

Relational deixis:

-King Uther:"There will be no more purges. Am I clear, **brother**?"

- Wife of Vortigern:"How do you know of this place,**my love**?"

Absolute deixis

-Sir Berdivere:"We would only seek to remind **Your Majesty**."

-Lord Mercia: "Are you sure about this, **my Lord**?"

The types of social relationship in King Arthur: Legend of Sword(2017)

Movie

Title :Sir Berdivere:"We would only seek to remind **Your Majesty**."

Clan :King Uther:"There will be no more purges. Am I clear, **brother**?"

Friendship: Arthur:"I think I found something that belongs to you, **Lack**."

In this work of art, amount of Relational deixis is more dominant than the Absolute deixis. It can be identified that the dominant deixis is a verbal elliptic that occurs because *King Arthur: Legend of Sword* is an action film, which is in the medieval background of the British Empire. This assumption is enriched because it also analyzed the context based on aspects of the speech situation.

To sum up, we have gained knowledge about social deixes through given examples above. From my point of view, using social deixes in literature gives some decoration and makes it understandable. Significantly it can provide new knowledge about how to communicate with others. Finally, social deixis is important for analysis because it can provide a reference in terms of communicating and knowing social culture in the middle Ages.

REFERENCES

1. Davis, RS (1997). *Comics: a Multidimensional Teaching in Integrated-Skill Classes*. Nagoyama University: Japan. (Online) Retrieved to February, 20, 2017 from (<http://www.esllab.com/research/comics.htm>)
2. Jamjuri. (2016). *Social deixis in elizabeth the golden age movie script*. UIN Sunan Kalijaga. Yogyakarta. Retrived to February, 20, 2017, from <https://digilib.uinsuka.ac.id:80/id/eprint/19349>
3. Leech, Geoffrey. (1983). *Principle of Pragmatics*. London: Longman
4. Levinson, S. C. (1983). *Pragmatics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University.
5. Levinson, S. C. (2000). *Presumptive Meaning: Theory of Generalized Conversational Implicature*. Cambridge: Cambridge University
6. Lyons, J. (1981). *Language and Linguistics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University.
7. Moleong, Lexy J. (2010). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya Offset.
8. Mokodompit, W. S. (2013). *Analysis of deixis in short story "the little mermaid" by Hans Christian Andersen*. University of Negeri Gorontalo. Gorontalo. Retrived to February, 20, 2017, from <http://kim.ung.ac.id/index.php/KIMFSB/article/download/3297/3273>
9. Peccei, J.S. (1999). *Pragmatics*. London: Routledge.

7. Rosmawaty. (2013). A Analysis the use of the kind of deixis on „ ayat-ayat cinta”

novel by habiburrahman el- shirazy. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science. Retrieved to February, 20, 2017, from http://www.ijhssnet.com/journals/Vol_3_No_17_September_2013/8.pdf.

Saeed, John I. (2000). Semantics. Malden: Blackwell Publisher.

8. Sinulingga, J. & Rafina. (2012). Deixis in inside sumatera magazine. University of

Medan, Medan. Retrived to February, 20, 2017 from

<http://download.portalgaruda.org/article.php?article=126767&val=3892>.

9. Yule, G., (1996). Pragmatics. New York: Oxford University Press.

10. Zainuddin, & Samosir, N. B. (2012). An analysis of dexis in the article of the Jakarta

post. University of Medan, Medan. Retrieved to February, 20, 2017 from

<http://download.portalgaruda.org/article.php/article/=15218069>

